

Effect of social support on stress level of secondary students of state board of Ahmedabad

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Abstract— Background: It has been observed that there has been a lot of stress among students related to studies. Various factors play an important role in escalating this stress which include genetic, environmental, family, friends etc. Early detection of these may help in the prevention of stress level. Present study focuses on finding whether the social support helps in reducing this stress or not.

Objectives: To assess the effect of social support on stress level of the male and female secondary students of Ahmedabad.

Methods: The sample size was 100 students of state board schools of Ahmedabad of which 50 boys and 50 girls were taken. The social support scale and the students stress scale was used.

Results: It has been observed that social support plays an important role in a student's life and it may affect the stress level of the student. More the support, less are the chances of getting stressed.

Conclusion: The conclusion is that social support can have a greater impact on the stress level of the secondary students.

Keywords: Students stress, social support, state board, stress.

I. INTRODUCTION

The students at the secondary level are at the stage where their academic performance plays an important role as it leads to a path where they are suppose to choose their career and have to give their best. Obviously this creates a stress for them as they are in a state of confusion and indecisiveness where it is difficult for them to make a selection for the stream they need to choose. Keeping this in mind there are few theories of the experts on the basis of which it can be understood that how stress affects a person. Students receive support from different places – family, friends, peers etc. Some face positive support and others seem to be less fortunate in getting it. Definition of support has changed gradually and in such changing situations what impact does it have need to be known in present times. “Various types of high stress, including daily stressors (Almeida, 2005) and major life events (Brown & Harris, 1989; Chappel, Suldo, & Ogg, 2014), have significant impact that may lead to negative psychological and physical health-related consequences among individuals”.

In few years, there's an alarming rise in stress levels among the students due to disturbed interpersonal relationships, academic stress, peer pressure etc. Taking into consideration the stress levels from previous study findings it indicated that the number of students who have a feeling of being overwhelmed has increased dramatically over the years Thus, stress seems to be a significant health problem for the students due to the environment producing various academic, social, and personal challenges they may come across. When the students have extremely high stress level or when they look at stress in a negative way, there are chances that they frequently experience more physical and psychological issues compared to those who have lower stress levels. Observing the fact that high stress and mental health problems have gradually increased overtime among the students, further studies are clearly needed to move towards evidence-based practices for this population who are at high risk. Seeking positive emotional and supportive relationships is the need of a person.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

Frances Hoferichter, Jonne Lohilahti, Miriam Hufenbach, Hans Jörgen Grabe, Geja Hageman and Diana Raufelder (2024) in their study tried to examine the neglected biophysiological process by other researchers who just focused on the self-report data. The researchers in this study examined whether the social support buffers the interplay of self-reported stress taking into consideration the biophysiological markers (i.e., cortisol, alpha-amylase, oxidative stress, and telomere length).

Moye Xin, Chengxi Yang, Lijin Zhang, Chenzhuo Gao and Sasa Wang (2024). In this study the researchers aimed to find out the specific mechanisms in the Post-COVID Era linking the variables and the distinguished role of online social support which remained relatively unexplored. 1180 university students from Northwestern China had participated in this study. Results showed that males reported a higher risk with reference to punishment and interpersonal relationships as compared to females. Whereas females experienced showed higher levels of pressure of learning as compared to those of males.

Merlin Josepha and Sudhesh N.T.(2023) conducted the study on 200 International students aged 18-30 years from various colleges and universities across India. Study analysis showed significant relationships among academic stress, lifestyle, achievement and social support. Better adjustment and quality social support systems led to a decrease in academic stress. Perceptions of Academic Stress (PAS) Scale, Multidimensional Scale of Perceived Social Support (MSPSS) and Academic Adjustment Scale were used in this study. The findings of this study insisted on implementing a holistic approach to reduce academic stress and adjustment concerns of international students'. Also, steps should be taken to ensure social support to enrich students' academic journey in a foreign country

Nurul Azizah, Abdul Aziz, Nur Sakinah Baharudin, Noor Amiera Alias (2022). This study assessed the relationship among stress and social support among the undergraduate students of Health Sciences. A cross-sectional study through convenience sampling method was used on 290 undergraduate Health Sciences students in public universities. The Perceived Stress Scale (PSS-10) was used to measure the perception of stress, and the Multidimensional Scale of Perceived Social Support (MSPSS) was used to measure perceived social support from three sources, including family, friends and significant others. The study suggested that for students to go through the stress of tough times social support from family is the strongest. It also reflected the need of stress management among undergraduate students for physical and psychological well-being. Further studies which include other academic fields and qualitative research can provide useful information on perceived social support among the students.

Rebecca Maymon and Nathan C. Hall (2021). The researchers in this study had included a focused search on social support, coping and stress among undergraduate students studying in first year. This review extended to conduct studies on social support particularly through different sources like peers, family, faculty, institution, and other support sources. A synthesis and critique of the literature explored presented the themes in the empirical research, as well as considerations for future research.

Ms. Neelima Bhargav and Dr. Shruti Tiwari (2020) in their study attempted to find a correlation through statistical analysis between role of social support and academic stress for school students of senior classes. A survey of randomly selected 600 students of class XI schools was done in the Rajasthan state of India. Academic Stress Scale and Social support scale were used to conduct this research. Students' responses were qualitatively analysed on both the scales by applying Pearson Correlation coefficient. Findings revealed that there is a noteworthy relationship between role of social support and over all academic stress.

Significance of study

This study will help in preventing increased stress level of the students through individual and group therapies which if not treated may lead to anxiety and depression which may further affect the physical, emotional and psychological well-being of the students and people around them. Early intervention would be helpful in healing a person suffering from stress.

III. OBJECTIVES

To assess the effect of social support and stress level among the secondary students of state board of Ahmedabad.

Hypothesis

H0 - There is no significant difference between the effect of social support and stress level of the secondary students of state board of Ahmedabad

H1 - There is no significant difference between the effect of social support and stress level of the male students of state board of Ahmedabad

H2 - There is no significant difference between the effect of social support and stress level of the female students of state board of Ahmedabad

IV. METHODOLOGY

Sample and Source of Sample The sample are the students of std.10th and 12th of Ahmedabad.

Sample Size The sample size is 100

Table

Students	Male	Female	Total
10 th	25	25	50
12 th	25	25	50
Total	50	50	100

Variables

Independent Variable

Social support

Dependent Variable

Stress level

Questionnaire / Tools used

- 1) Social support scale
- 2) Students stress scale

Research Design : 2x2 design would be used

V. STATISTICAL ANALYSIS

Mean, standard deviation, standard error mean, difference, t-value and level of significance are used as a statistical technique to find out the aim.

Table 1

Students	N	Mean	S.D	SED	't' value	Level of Significance
Social Support	100	89	10.04	1	-25.6	Not Significant
Students Stress	100	152	22.51	2.25		

In the "t" distribution table at df =100 the "t" value at.01 level is 2.62. The obtained "t" value (-25.6) is much less than this value, hence it is not significant and null hypothesis is rejected.

Table 2

Students	N	Mean	S.D	SED	't' value	Level of Significance
Social Support	50	89	9.26	1.30	-8.55	Not Significant
Students Stress	50	146	46.19	6.53		

In the “t” distribution table at df =50 the “t” value at.01 level is 2.67. The obtained “t” value (-8.55) is less than this value, hence it is not significant and null hypothesis is rejected.

Table 3

Students	N	Mean	S.D	SED	‘t’ value	Level of Significance
Social Support	50	88	10.70	1.51	-18.13	Not Significant
Students Stress	50	159	25.54	1.61		

In the “t” distribution table at df =50 the “t” value at.01 level is 2.67. The obtained “t” value (-8.55) is less than this value, hence it is not significant and null hypothesis is rejected.

VI. RESULT AND DISCUSSION

It has been observed that social support plays an important role in a student’s life and it may affect the stress level of the student. More the support, less are the chances of getting stressed.

VII. CONCLUSION

The conclusion is that social support can have a greater impact on the stress level of the secondary students.

LIMITATIONS AND SUGGESTIONS

The limitation of this study is that its sample size is small, gender and area not taken into consideration and also the streams can be explored. The results may vary with increase in sample size, adding gender and also other educational streams and area. The study needs to be continued further and explored more.

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